

Integrating GIS, Earth Observation, UAV Imagery, and AI for Precision Fertigation with Reclaimed Water in Apricot Orchards

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doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20407992

Abstract: Reclaimed water from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) offers a sustainable irrigation alternative in water-scarce Mediterranean regions, yet its variable nutrient composition demands intelligent management. This study presents an operational Decision Support System (DSS) integrating Sentinel-2 imagery, multispectral UAV data, WWTP IoT telemetry, and ensemble machine learning for weekly fertigation prescription in a 1.36 ha apricot orchard in southeast Spain. A biophysical cascade converts Sentinel-2 reflectance (338 observations, 2019–2026) into weekly water-use efficiency (WUE) over a 151-cell, 10×10 m grid. Of three candidate models (LightGBM, XGBoost, MLP), the MLP achieved the best validation scores, an ensemble strategy further reduced WUE forecast error (MAE = 0.106 gC m⁻² mm⁻¹, R² = 0.990). Both crop demand and effluent quality predictions feed a constrained optimisation maximising reclaimed-water use subject to six restrictions: ETr demand, bilateral NPK bounds, EC phytotoxicity, Nitrates Directive ceiling, soil moisture, and WWTP flow. The optimiser covers 100 % of the WWTP-zone demand with effluent (15.33 m³), the nutrient credit supplies 6.4 % of N and 27.8 % of P₂O₅. DSS value lies primarily in freshwater substitution and regulatory compliance.

Keywords: reclaimed water fertigation; water use efficiency; Sentinel-2; decision support system; ensemble machine learning.

1 Introduction

Water scarcity is a major challenge for semi-arid Mediterranean agriculture, in south-east Spain irrigation accounts for roughly 70% of freshwater withdrawals. Reuse of WWTP effluent reduces freshwater abstraction while recycling plant-available N, P and K (EU Regulation 2020/741). However, for fruit orchards in Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) vulnerable zones, the nutrient load of reclaimed water is simultaneously an asset and a regulatory risk, as the Directive caps application at 170 kg N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Existing AI models for wastewater reuse target discharge standards, not crop demand (Mainardis et al. 2022, Liu et al. 2025), and none couples satellite-derived demand with stochastic effluent quality under regulatory constraints. This paper presents an operational DSS for weekly reclaimed-water fertigation prescription in an apricot orchard in south-east Spain.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

The study site is a 1.36 ha apricot orchard (*Prunus armeniaca* L., cv. Búlida) in Murcia, Spain (semi-arid

Mediterranean, ≈270 mm yr⁻¹, concentrated in spring and autumn). The plot comprises a reclaimed-water zone (0.09 ha, irrigated exclusively with treated effluent) and a control zone (1.27 ha, regular irrigation system). The spatial analysis unit is a 10×10 m grid (151 cells), each labelled by zone and propagated through all subsequent calculations.

2.2 Data sources

The DSS integrates five data sources: (i) Sentinel-2 L2A images (10 m, ≈5d, 11 bands B01–B12 + SCL via the CDSE API) feed the biophysical cascade. This 5-day sliding window contains cloud screening (<10 %, SCL classes 8–9–10) and temporal gap-filling yields 338 valid observations (January 2019–March 2026), (ii) historical meteorological forcing comes from ERA5-Land via Open-Meteo (0.1°, T, RH, wind at 2 m per Allen et al. (1998), Rg, soil moisture at three depths, ET₀, soil T), used for training and validation, (iii) operational forecasts (d+7/d+14) rely on the Weatherbit API (point location, 16 d horizon, daily: T, RH, wind, precipitation, cloud cover), with solar radiation estimated via Ångström–Prescott (Allen et al. 1998) when not directly available, (iv) WWTP IoT sensors daily recording NO₃, NH₄, totalN, totalP, PO₄, EC concentrations and total flow, supplying nutrient credit and effluent prediction inputs, and (v) multispectral UAV flights (10 bands, GSD ≈5 cm) capture tree-level heterogeneity invisible at Sentinel-2 resolution.

2.3 Sentinel-2 biophysical cascade

Per-cell (10×10 m) radiometric statistics are extracted by intersecting each S2-L2A image with the 151-cell grid. The cascade converts reflectance into NDVI, NDMI, fPAR (via fractional cover and LAI, Lambert–Beer), GPP, NPP, ETr, WUE and soil moisture. GPP follows light-use efficiency (Monteith, 1972): GPP = LUE · fPAR · PAR, with LUE = 1.92 gC MJ⁻¹ (Ruimy et al. 1996). NPP incorporates autotrophic respiration with Q10 correction (R_{auto,ref} = 0.47, Q10 = 2.0, T_{ref} = 15 °C). ET₀ follows Penman–Monteith FAO-56 (Allen et al. 1998). ETr is partitioned via dual-source ETLook (Bastiaanssen et al. 2014). Soil moisture (0–7 cm) is predicted by a Random Forest calibrated against ERA5-Land using six predictors (NDMI, 7-day precipitation, 7-day ET₀, soil temperature, sine and cosine of the day of the year). Validation of the pipeline ET₀ against ERA5-Land reanalysis yielded R² = 0.993 and RMSE = 0.32 mm d⁻¹, the surrogate soil moisture model achieved R² = 0.881. Annual erosion is estimated via RUSLE: A = R·K·LS·C·P (Renard et al. 1997). UAV flights covered the entire plot, allowing 55 individual trees to be delineated using GMM models, and the same six physiological variables were extracted as those obtained via Sentinel-2. Tree-level statistics validate

the satellite-derived NDVI and ETr estimates and generate spatial correction factors for prescription maps.

2.4 Predictive models

WWTP effluent variables (NO_3 , NH_4 , totalN, totalP, EC, daily flow) are forecasted at d+7 and d+14 via a two-model fallback system: a SARIMA time-series model (minimum 60 valid days) or a seasonal moving-average trend from equivalent periods of previous years (minimum 30 days). Each prediction carries a confidence label propagated to the optimisation layer. Weekly NDVI, NPP, ETr and WUE are forecast at plot and cell scale (10×10 m) using an ensemble of three candidate model families: LightGBM (Ke et al. 2017), XGBoost (Chen and Guestrin 2016) and a Multilayer Perceptron. Hyperparameter optimisation uses Optuna (Akiba et al. 2019) with the TPE sampler and sub-sampled walk-forward cross-validation. These three families were selected to span complementary learning strategies: gradient-boosted trees (LightGBM, XGBoost) for tabular feature interactions, and a neural network (MLP) for capturing non-linear temporal patterns in the biophysical time series.

2.5 Decision engine and fertigation optimisation

The decision engine integrates d+7 crop demand (ETr/WUE) and effluent quality predictions to prescribe, per management zone, the reclaimed-water volume and supplementary mineral NPK dose. Prior to optimisation, raw ETr demand per zone is adjusted by a physiological decision matrix crossing two signals: productive trajectory (cumulative NPP ratio vs. historical p50 for the same week) and integrated water-use efficiency (iWUE ratio vs. historical p75), applying correction factors from -0.15 to $+0.15$ depending on the combination, a second factor modulates demand by soil moisture status. The WWTP-zone optimisation maximises reclaimed-water volume subject to six constraints: (i) adjusted ETr demand, (ii) bilateral NPK bounds from the cooperative's monthly

fertilisation plan, (iii) EC phytotoxicity (≤ 3.0 mS/cm), (iv) annual Nitrates Directive ceiling (170 kg N ha^{-1}), (v) soil moisture status, and (vi) available WWTP flow. The nutrient shortfall between the effluent credit and the cooperative's plan is met with exogenous fertiliser. Prescriptions are exported as JSON and GeoTIFF.

3 Results

3.1 WUE monitoring and forecasting

Figure 1 shows the spatial WUE pattern for the most recent observed week (2026-W11, 9–15 March). The control zone (142 cells) exhibits higher values than the nine WWTP cells (orange boundary), consistent with the historically lower NDVI recorded under reclaimed-water fertigation in this orchard. Of the three candidate model families evaluated (LightGBM, XGBoost, MLP), the MLP achieved the best individual validation scores for all four targets: NPP (MAE = 0.084 $\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$, $R^2 = 0.992$), ETr (MAE = 0.060 mm d^{-1} , $R^2 = 0.995$), and direct WUE prediction. An ensemble strategy combining the MLP direct WUE prediction with the ratio of the MLP-predicted NPP and ETr (weighting factor $\alpha = 0.85$) further reduced the WUE validation MAE to 0.106 $\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{mm}^{-1}$ ($R^2 = 0.990$, Table 1). Spatial disaggregation applied the ensemble-predicted temporal change to the last observed cell-level map. The d+7 forecast for week 12 (16–22 March 2026) yields a plot-level WUE of 3.35 $\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{mm}^{-1}$ (90 % CI [2.98, 3.73]), control cells average 3.39 and WWTP cells 2.73. No stress alerts were triggered.

3.2 Weekly reclaimed-water prescription

Table 2 summarises the weekly fertigation prescription issued by the decision engine for week 12. The optimiser allocates 15.33 m^3 of reclaimed water to the WWTP zone (0.09 ha), the full irrigation is thus met with treated effluent and no standard irrigation water is needed. The control zone (1.27 ha) receives 238.03 m^3 from the usual water irrigation system. The nutrient credit supplies 42.3 g N and

Figure 1. Observed WUE ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{mm}^{-1}$) over the 151-cell, 10×10 m Sentinel-2 grid covering the 1.36 ha apricot orchard in Murcia (SE Spain), week of 9–15 March 2026 (2026-W11). The orange boundary delimits the nine WWTP treatment cells receiving reclaimed water fertigation.

135.6 g P₂O₅ (6.4% and 27.8% of weekly requirements). The optimiser prescribes supplementation with exogenous N (618.4 g), P₂O₅ (351.9 g) and K₂O (251.4 g), respecting NPK bounds, the Nitrates Directive ceiling (170 kg N ha⁻¹) and EC phytotoxicity (≤ 3.0 mS cm⁻¹). Control-zone fertilisation is entirely exogenous.

Table 1. Ensemble ML model performance and d+7 forecast (week 12, 16–22 March 2026) by zone.

Target	Model	Val_MAE	d+7 Control	d+7 WWTP
WUE (gC m ⁻² mm ⁻¹)	Ensemble MLP	0.106	3.39	2.73

Table 2. Weekly fertigation prescription from the decision engine for week 12 (16–22 March 2026).

Parameter	Unit	WWTP zone	Control zone	Total orchard
WWTP water	m ³	15.33	—	15.33
Irrigation System water	m ³	0	238.03	238.03
N from WWTP	g	42.3	—	42.3
P ₂ O ₅ from WWTP	g	135.6	—	135.6
N exogenous	g	618.4	10,259.1	10,877.5
P ₂ O ₅ exogenous	g	351.9	7,569.3	7,921.2
K ₂ O exogenous	g	251.4	3,903.7	4,155.1

4 Discussion

REUTIVAR (Alcaide Zaragoza et al. 2019, 2020), the closest existing system, computes real-time olive-orchard fertigation from weather and water quality data, demonstrating that reclaimed water reduces exogenous N. However, it operates without remote sensing, deriving crop water needs from tabulated Kc coefficients with no intra-plot resolution. Lin et al. (2020) proposed ILP-based IoT greenhouse fertigation at point-sensor scale without Earth Observation. In remote sensing-based irrigation, Guzinski et al. (2023) achieved 0.84 mm d⁻¹ RMSE for field-scale ETr fusing Sentinel-2/3 and Landsat, and Martínez-Guanter et al. (2023) assimilated Sentinel-2 biophysical variables into a vineyard digital twin for automated scheduling. More broadly, Saggi and Jain (2022) surveyed ML approaches to smart irrigation scheduling, concluding that most systems address either water quantity or nutrient management in isolation rather than jointly. None of the reviewed systems couples satellite-derived crop demand with stochastic WWTP effluent quality under explicit regulatory constraints. Our DSS differs in three respects: (i) the biophysical cascade runs from Sentinel-2 reflectance to forecast weekly WUE, feeding crop water demand and carbon productivity directly into the optimiser, (ii) effluent quality prediction at d+7 and d+14, propagating confidence labels from the fallback model hierarchy, enables operational anticipation unavailable in spot-sampling systems, and (iii) the analytical constrained optimisation enforces six simultaneous bounds (adjusted ETr demand, bilateral NPK plan, EC phytotoxicity, Nitrates Directive, soil

moisture and WWTP flow), yielding a feasible weekly prescription.

Week-12 results show that effluent meets the full WWTP-zone water demand (15.33 m³) but only 6.4% of weekly N and 27.8% of P₂O₅. For a small municipal WWTP the nutrient credit is modest, and exogenous fertilisation remains predominant. System utility is highly dependent on two factors: available WWTP flow, which governs the irrigable fraction of the orchard, and effluent nutrient concentration, which exhibits considerable seasonal and spatial variability as documented by Mainardis et al. (2022) and Alcaide Zaragoza et al. (2022) for nitrogen in olive-orchard distribution networks. With higher WWTP-to-orchard area ratios or more concentrated effluents (e.g. agro-industrial wastewater), fertiliser savings would increase proportionally. The validation results of section 2.3 confirm that the biophysical cascade produces reliable inputs for the optimisation layer, although the soil moisture estimate would benefit from future integration of Sentinel-1 SAR backscatter data for cloud-independent surface moisture retrieval.

5 Conclusions

(i) The DSS demonstrates feasibility of coupling Sentinel-2-derived demand with stochastic effluent quality in a joint water-NPK optimisation under regulatory constraints (ensemble MLP MAE = 0.106 gC m⁻² mm⁻¹, R² = 0.990), (ii) Reclaimed water covers 100% of WWTP-zone demand but only 6.4% of weekly N: the primary value is freshwater substitution, scaling with the WWTP-to-orchard area ratio, (iii) the prescription is transferable to Mediterranean cooperatives, pending multi-year agronomic validation.

Acknowledgements: This work was funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation through the iRAIN project (ref. MIG-20232038, TransMisiones call 2023–2026), co-financed by the Centre for Industrial Technological Development (CDTI) and the European Union.

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